

SRINIVAS INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT STUDIES

Mangalore-575001, Karnataka State

NIRF Ranking 2017

Self-Evaluation Based Score = 96.2/100

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Parameter 1 : Teaching, Learning & Resources; Marks =100; Weightage = 30%				Marks allotted
A	Student Strength (SS): 20 Marks	MBA Student Intake = 120 MCA Student Intake = 60	Students Admitted = 111 Student Admitted = 45	18/20
B	Faculty-student ratio with emphasis on permanent faculty (FSR): 30 marks	MBA Number of Faculty = 16 MCA Number of Faculty = 8	Faculty-student ratio = 1:14 Faculty-student ratio = 1:12	25/30
C	Combined metric for Faculty with PhD (or equivalent) and Experience (FQE): 20 marks	Faculty with Ph.D. = 5	Faculty with average Experience = 12 years	15/20
D	Financial Resources and their Utilisation (FRU): 30 Marks	Fee Collection 60,000/Student	Expenditure /Student 60,000/Student	30/30
Total Marks out of 100				88/100

Parameter 2 : Research and Professional Practice (RP) Ranking weight: 0.30				Marks allotted
A	Combined metric for Publications (PU): 30 marks	Number of Journal Publications during 2016 = 177 Number of Faculty members = 24	(Publications)/(Faculty) = (P/F) Ratio = 7.4 Note : (P/F) ratio is less than one for all Indian B-Schools.	30/30
B	Combined metric for Quality of Publications (QP): 40 marks	Citations during 2016 = 850 Papers published during 2015 = 85	Average Citations per paper /year = AC/T = 10 Note : (AC/T) ratio is less than one for all Indian B-Schools.	40/40
C	IPR and Patents: Filed, Published, Granted and Licensed (IPR): 15 marks	Study Books & Edited Books Published during 2016 = 48	Average books/Faculty for the year 2016 = 2	15/15

D	Footprint of Projects, Professional Practice and Executive Development Programs (FPPP): 15 marks	Projects executed under Research Centres = 40	Average number of Projects/ Faculty = 2	15/15
Total Marks out of 100				100/100

Parameter 3 : Graduation Outcomes (GO) Ranking weight: 0.20				Marks allotted
A	Combined metric for Placement, Higher Studies, and Entrepreneurship (GPHE): 40 marks	Placement = 76% Higher Studies = 5 % Own Business = 19 %	100 % Occupied with no unemployment	40/40
B	Metric for University Examinations(GUE): 40 marks	University Exam Result = 100% pass	Academic performance based on University Result = 100%	40/40
C	Median Salary (GMS): 20 marks	Average salary/Student =300 K/Student. Average Fee/Student = 60 K/student.	Average Return for first year on Investment (ARI) = 300/60 = 5. Note : The ARI of Indian Top B-schools is less than 3.	20/20
D	Metric for Graduating Students Admitted Into Top Universities (GTOP): 15 marks	Not Applicable for P.G. Course		-
E	Metric for Number of Ph.D. Students Graduated (GPHD): 10 marks	Not Applicable for P.G. Course		-
Total Marks out of 100				100/100

Parameter 4 : Outreach and Inclusivity (OI) Ranking, weight: 0.10				Marks allotted
A	Percent Students from other states/countries (Region Diversity RD): 30 marks	Total number of Students = 111 Other State Students = 44	RD = OS/T = 40 %	28/30
B	Percentage of Women (Women Diversity WD): 25 mark	Total number of Students = 111 Women Students = 50	WP = 45 %	25/25

C	Economically and Socially Challenged Students (ESCS): 25 marks	Total number of Students = 120. Economically and Socially Challenged Students = 60	ECCS = 56 %	25/25
D	Facilities for Physically Challenged Students (PCS): 20 marks	(1) Ramp (2) Physically Challenged Students Toilet, (3) Wheel Chair	PCS = 100 %	20/20
Total Marks out of 100				98/100

Parameter 5 : Perception (PR) Ranking weight: 0.10				Marks allotted
A	Peer Perception: Employers and Research Investors (PREMP): 25 marks	Industry Projects	100 %	25/25
B	Peer Perception: Academic Peers (PRACD): 25 marks	Research Conferences	100 %	25/25
C	Public Perception (PRPUB): 25 marks	Website Information	100 %	25/25
D	Competitiveness (PRCMP): 25 marks	Innovations & Best Practices	100 %	25/25
Total Marks out of 100				100/100

S. No.	Parameters	Marks Scored	Weightage	Marks Based on Weightage
1	Teaching, Learning & Resources	88/100	30%	26.4
2	Research and Professional Practice (RP)	100/100	30%	30
3	Graduation Outcomes (GO) Ranking	100/100	20%	20
4	Outreach and Inclusivity (OI)	98/100	10%	9.8
5	Perception (PR)	100/100	10%	10
Grand Total				96.2/100